

ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS AND SUSTAINABILITY PERCEPTION AND ATTITUDE OF GENERATION Z

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Environmental Awareness and Sustainability Perception and Attitude of Generation Z

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Abstract

As the world currently experiences an ecological crisis, the younger generation is urged to act on preserving nature by refocusing their minds on environmental discussions and adapting more sustainable behaviors. This study investigated the relationship between Environmental Awareness and Sustainability Perception and Attitude of Generation Z using a descriptive-correlational research design. This study is conducted on 382 Generation Z students (ages 18-25 years old) in a higher education institution in Davao City. The findings revealed that Generation Z students have a high level of Environmental Awareness ($\bar{x} = 3.98$) and very high Sustainability Perception and Attitude ($\bar{x} = 4.27$). Furthermore, there is a significant positive strong correlation between their level of environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude ($r = 0.568$). The results indicate that Generation Z students highly consider the importance of environmental awareness in their actions, and they have a high positive perception and attitude towards sustainable behavior. This revealed that with the Generation Z students' heightened knowledge and awareness in terms of the environment, there is also a heightened positive perception and attitude towards promoting sustainability with regards to the society, economy, and environment. To enhance the knowledge of students on environmental issues and orient their actions towards sustainability, the authors recommended for a stronger integration of environmental information in college curriculum. The authors also suggested the university to strengthen its pro-environment policies to empower more students to become conscious with their actions. It was also suggested for future researchers to further investigate the factors and mediating influences that could affect how students perceive the environment and the concept of sustainable development or use other generations as samples for comparison or another scope of study.

Keywords: *environmental awareness, sustainability perception and attitude, Generation Z*

Introduction

Environmental awareness means knowing how to confront environmental issues and the risks they bring. This constitutes many values, and viewpoints concerning the environment, as well as beliefs that contain actions that are transmitted to future generations (Gümürkçüoğlu et al., 2017). On the other hand, sustainable perception and attitude means evaluation of environmental problems, or of a personal event and attitude toward environmental conditions (Lin et al., 2021). Adopting a sustainable attitude lets people engage in ethical and environmentally friendly actions in both their personal and professional life (Amplio Global, 2021). According to Ackerman (2018), environmental psychology covers the interaction between people and environment where prominent areas include costs of human activities, psychological facets of people and nature, and consumer and environmental behaviors. However, Khoiri et al. (2021) found that environmental awareness is mostly overlooked by students as part of their character education. Some authors noted that this negligence influences their motives to protect and preserve the current environment and alleviate the damage that already exists, resulting in failure in fostering sustainability. Environmental degradation is a global concern perpetuated by the lack of adequate instruction, awareness, information, and approach of citizens towards nature and its resources (Yadav et al., 2022). Thus, education must shift its emphasis to encourage students to be environmentally aware (Dela Peña et al., 2018).

Although heightened awareness on sustainability and its relevant issues are of global interest, some university students still lack knowledge of it despite hearing the term from instructional resources, while majority of them are not involved in reutilizing renewable materials (Alsaati et al., 2020). In a study by Nahar et al. (2022) in Bangladesh, it was found that people have awareness of the necessity to adopt a pro-environmental mindset, but they do not engage in any environmental practice. Contrastingly, students in a region of India have a higher level of scientific attitude but low in terms of environmental awareness, indicating that they have not been exposed to the concrete stage and lower level of scientific literature that led to the difficulty in coping with the higher one (Danielraja, 2019). Meanwhile, a study by Punzalan (2020) in a private school sector in the Philippines revealed that students have a good level of environmental awareness but poor level of environmental practice. Pertaining to the role of Generation Z towards such principles, a study by Dabija et al. (2020) found that they have a favorable attitude to retailers that are promoting sustainable values not only in marketing, but also in production of green items. Some authors noted that Gen Zs are more oriented to technology, sustainability, and are greener in lifestyle. This indicates that involvement of Gen Zs in world affairs is far higher than that of earlier generations, and they have attitudes that are more attentive and conscious (Vorontsova et al., 2021). Similarly, climate change discussions may become a part of their transformative curriculum when Gen Zs see the commitment of their peers, and are urged to question their choices, power, authority, and decision-making participation (Barron et al., 2022).

Moreover, due to insufficient education, there is still a noticeable lack of interest in environmental conservation (Alsaati et al., 2020). Despite the initial survey stating that the younger generation desires better compensation more than older generations, the data imply that when people learn about the intrinsic nature of sustainable development goals, they may modify their behavior (Yamane & Kaneko,

2021). Nonetheless, research on how people perceive sustainability is limited; the same holds true for research on the link between sustainability perception and sustainable behavior (Yttredal & Homlong, 2020). Thus, it is vital to investigate the Generation Z regarding their environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude to bridge the gap of inadequate knowledge and limited studies on environmental and sustainability perspectives.

With the presented gaps and several research findings relevant to environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude, the main purpose of the study is to understand and investigate the significant relationship between environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude of Generation Z students in one of the higher education institutions in Davao City. Given that, it aims to determine the level of environmental awareness of the Generation Z students. Also, determine their level of sustainability perception and attitude. Furthermore, assess if there is a significant relationship between the level of environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude of Generation Z students.

Analyzing the relationship between environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude of Generation Z students will demonstrate whether their level of awareness towards the environment could be an influencing factor to how they perceive sustainability for its advantage. Through this study, the students or the Gen Zs in particular will be educated on the current environmental status and on practices that promote sustainability if it is proven that they garner low degrees in such variables. With this as a starting point, universities will conduct information drives and training to enhance the current curriculum and equip students with the knowledge regarding the current environmental state and the ways on how to become a sustainable citizen. This also serves as an additional research viewpoint for scholars who are interested in investigating environmental behaviors of students particularly in this era where environmental threats are becoming more prevalent. At large, this will benefit society, even those who do not belong in the Generation Z, by emphasizing the importance of collective awareness about environmental affairs and building a positive outlook toward a sustainable lifestyle for alleviating environmental crises.

This study is anchored on Hungerford and Volk's (1990, as cited in Akintude, 2017) Environmental Citizen Model, which proposes three stages of educational involvement ranging from first exposure to genuine involvement. It then suggests that each stage has specific knowledge and attitude characteristics. This model identifies numerous variables that must be present for a citizen to be environmentally literate which provides a foundation for categorizing and separating environmental literacy variables based on their importance. Furthermore, it provides a framework for determining an individual's level on the literacy ladder, allowing one to determine whether a citizen has grown to become an environmentally responsible citizen. Furthermore, the Behavioral Change Model proposed by Ramsey and Rickson (1976) implies a direct relationship with the premise that if people were better informed, they would become more aware of environmental problems. Thus, motivated them to behave in an environmentally responsible manner. With increased knowledge, environmentally favorable attitudes that lead to responsible environmental actions emerge. Consequently, it provides a foundation for exploring the possible relationships between ecological knowledge, environmental awareness, and attitude and how these can translate into action or inaction. With this distinction, the purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude among the Generation Z students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design or the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data. This was used to identify trends and averages, formulate hypotheses, examine causality, and extrapolate findings to larger populations (Bhandari, 2020). Specifically, it made use of a descriptive- correlational design that explains the variables and connections that emerge naturally between but does not try to demonstrate a causal connection (Noah, 2021). This research design ensured that the variables shared by participants that can affect the results are equally distributed among groups using a criterion. It guided the researchers in finding the significant relationship between environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude of Generation Zs.

Respondents

The research respondents were the students who belong in the Generation Z (1997-2012) studying in one of the higher education institutions in Davao City. They were selected using quota sampling, a non-probability sampling technique in which the samples are gathered and contain the same proportions of individuals as the entire population in terms of known characteristics, traits, or focused phenomena (Simkus, 2022). The target samples were a total of 382 participants, wherein participants must be from birth years of 18–25-year-olds to participate in the study. Furthermore, those students who do not belong in the Generation Z age range and are not affiliated with the institution were not catered to in this study. The participants were thereafter given the logical choice of declining the survey at any time, either before or during the data gathering as the researchers have no control over their free will.

Instrument

The researchers had utilized a questionnaire that is composed of two sections. The first section is a standardized questionnaire called the Environmental Consciousness Survey that was developed by Eren and Yaqub (2015). The second section is a questionnaire adapted from Balakrishnan, et. al (2019) which is called Perception and Attitudes toward Sustainable Development Questionnaire. All of these were integrated into one questionnaire to assess the students' level of environmental awareness and level of sustainability perception

and attitude, as well as examine the relationship between these two variables.

The Environmental Consciousness Survey utilized a five-point Likert scale for the four indicators: conscious consumption, waste and recycling, energy saving, and sustainable environment. There was a total of 28 questions that were asked to students, 5 questions regarding their conscious use and consumption of environmental impacting things, 8 questions for waste and recycling, 3 questions for energy saving, and 12 questions for sustainable environment. On the other hand, the Perception and Attitudes toward Sustainable Development Questionnaire utilized a five-point Likert scale with two indicators: attitude and perception. The two indicators have 12 questions each, so the questionnaire has 24 questions in total. Hence, the questionnaire includes three key dimensions of sustainability: social, economy, and environment.

Table 1. Rating Scale for Environmental Consciousness Survey

Scale	Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very High	This indicates that students' actions highly consider the importance of environmental awareness.
4	3.41 – 4.20	High	This indicates that students' actions consider the importance of environmental awareness.
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	This indicates that students' actions impartial towards the importance of environmental awareness.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Low	This indicates that students' actions disregard the importance of environmental awareness.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	This indicates that students highly disregard the importance of environmental awareness.

Table 2. Rating Scale for Sustainability Perception and Attitude Questionnaire

Scale	Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very High	This indicates that there is a high positive perception and attitude towards sustainability.
4	3.41 – 4.20	High	This indicates that there is a positive perception and attitude towards sustainability.
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	This indicates that there is a moderate perception and attitude towards sustainability.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Low	This indicates that there is a negative perception and attitude towards sustainability.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	This indicates that there is a high negative perception and attitude towards sustainability.

Procedure

The following steps that were followed in gathering the data for the study are:

Permission to Conduct the Study. Before conducting the study, the researchers asked permission from their research adviser and dean of the College of Arts and Sciences and Education. Afterwards, the researchers obtained the formal approval of the BS Psychology program head of the university to conduct the research.

Distribution of the Questionnaire. After the approval was granted, the researchers started administering the survey questionnaire to the Generation Z students inside the premise of the university. In the process, the researchers disclosed the rationale of the study and dispensed an informed consent to inform participants regarding potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw participation.

Retrieval of Data. After administering the survey questionnaire, the researchers personally obtained the responses from the participants. The data was then encoded prior to data analysis. Also, the physical data was safeguarded by the researchers to protect their privacy.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data. A statistician from the university was in charge of the data analysis using the appropriate statistical tools with the help of SPSS Statistics software. Specific research questions and test hypotheses was followed through in the data interpretation to assess the results and establish conclusions from the study.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools that were used to provide analysis and interpretation of the results are:

Mean. To obtain the average level of environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude of participants, this descriptive statistical tool was utilized. The mean refers to the arithmetic average or summary of a set or group of two or more numbers (Hayes, 2022).

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r). To analyze the significant relationship between environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude, this statistical treatment was used. This inferential statistical tool is the most often used metric for determining a linear relationship. It ranges from -1 to 1 that indicates the strength and direction of a link between two variables. This means that coefficient (r) of 0 means no relationship, between 0 and 1 has positive correlation, and between 0 and -1 has negative correlation (Turney, 2022).

Ethical Considerations

The following ethical considerations that were strictly observed before, during, and after the conduct of the study are:

Informed Consent. The researchers had informed the participants about the study's purpose. Participants were fully informed about what was expected of them, how the data would be used, and the potential consequences. To participate in the research, participants

must provide explicit, active, signed consent, which includes understanding their rights to access their information and the ability to withdraw at any time (Fleming & Zegwaard, 2018).

Voluntary Participation. The participants must have freely chosen to be involved in the information gathering process and should not be coerced into participating (Peer Connect, 2022). The researchers respected the participants' right to participate by emphasizing that their participation is voluntary. The respondents were given the opportunity to agree or disagree with the study at this point. Nevertheless, researchers were obligated to respect the decision.

Confidentiality. The researchers preserved the identities and sensitive information of the participants strictly confidential. Maintaining participants' privacy and confidentiality protects them from potential harms such as psychological distress or embarrassment, social harms, and criminal or civil liability (UCI Office of Research, 2018). Participants, however, had the right to be protected from harm or unauthorized invasion of privacy, as well as to be treated with dignity. To avoid data breaches, researchers had only collected the data required for the study.

Data Storage and Disposal. The researchers had ensured that private information was secured and not disclosed to unauthorized parties. The information gathered from the participants for paper-based personal data must be kept in a locked storage container, such as a filing cabinet in a locked office; for digital data, password-protected or, preferably, encrypted storage must be used. When data is no longer needed for reference, it would be deleted, destroyed, or otherwise disposed of.

Fabrication and Deceit. The researchers ensured that there was no false information, or any non-existent findings that were used or presented in the study through proper imposing of criteria, and the data that was collected was only from the selected participants fitted in the study. According to Bos (2020) it is necessary to keep all evidence from the sources as reference to counter any claim of deceit and fabrication. Moreover, all the findings were recorded to avoid any misinterpretation of information.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the discussion and analysis of the results in accordance with the research objectives of the study.

Profile of the Respondents

The results of this study were determined from the 382 respondents who answered the survey conducted face-to-face. Specifically, the respondents chosen were the Generation Z (18 to 25 years old) students currently enrolled at a Higher Education Institution in the academic years 2022–2023. Presented in Table 3 is the profile of the respondents for the study.

Table 3. Profile of the Respondents

<i>Department</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Actual Sample Size</i>
College of Accounting Education (CAE)	2,241	37
College of Architecture and Fine Arts Education (CAFAE)	1,670	28
College of Arts and Sciences Education (CASE)	2,336	37
College of Computing Education (CCE)	1,619	26
College of Criminal Justice Education (CCJE)	3,097	51
College of Engineering Education (CEE)	4,996	81
College of Hospitality Education (CHE)	1,659	27
College of Health and Sciences Education (CHSE)	1,529	25
College of Teacher Education (CTE)	2,052	33
College of Business Administration Education (CBAE)	2,319	37
Overall	23,488	382

Level of Environmental Awareness of Generation Z Students

The level of environmental awareness of Generation Z students is demonstrated in Table 4. This includes the mean, standard deviation, and descriptive level of the data gathered from 382 respondents.

Table 4. Level of Environmental Awareness of Generation Z Students

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Conscious Consumption	3.70	0.670	High
Waste and Recycling	3.90	0.644	High
Energy Saving	4.24	0.800	Very High
Sustainable Environment	4.10	0.632	High
Environmental Awareness	3.98	0.551	High

For the level of environmental awareness, the data was generated from the mean of its four indicators: (1) Conscious Consumption, (2) Waste and Recycling, (3) Energy Saving, and (4) Sustainable Environment.

For the first indicator, Conscious Consumption, the mean score is 3.70 which indicates a high level. For the second indicator, Waste and Recycling, the mean score is 3.90 which indicates a high level. Meanwhile, the third indicator, which is Energy Saving, has a mean score of 4.24, indicating a very high level. For the fourth indicator, Sustainable Environment, the mean score is 4.10 which indicates a high level. Overall, the 382 respondents obtained a mean score of 3.98, which indicates that their level of environmental awareness is high. Furthermore, the four indicators, Conscious Consumption, Waste and Recycling, Energy Saving, and Sustainable Environment have obtained standard deviations of 0.670, 0.644, 0.800, and 0.632 respectively. This means that the data points of these indicators are clustered around the mean. Overall, the level of environmental awareness has obtained a standard deviation of 0.551 which means that there is less variability of the responses.

Since the Conscious Consumption, Energy Saving, and Sustainable Environment indicators are on high levels, while the Waste and Recycling is very high, the overall level of environmental awareness is high as well. This suggests that Generation Z students highly consider the importance of environmental awareness in their actions. Thus, this confirmed Hungerfolk and Volk's (1990 as cited in Akintude, 2017) Environmental Citizen model which emphasizes the importance of environmental literacy to an individual in order for them to become environmentally responsible citizens. With the high level of environmental awareness this allowed them to possess competences that enable them to act in the interest of the environment.

As highlighted in the study of Vorontsova et al. (2021), most Gen Z tourism and business students in St. Petersburg manifests a high degree of environmental awareness which is practice-oriented in nature. Students revealed that the escalating ecological issues piqued their interest, and they decided to allow innovative technology, eco-friendly materials, and development of professional skills throughout their training. In a similar manner, Generation Zs in United Kingdom also showed strong awareness and desire towards ethical and environmental issues as driven by their unlimited exposure to information published on social media platforms and online resources (Djafarova & Foots, 2022). Thus, it contradicts the finding of Alsaati et al. (2020) that some university students still lack knowledge of the environment despite hearing it from instructional resources, while also negating the observations of Danielraja (2019) that students in India have a higher level of scientific attitude but low in terms of environmental awareness. Lastly, it disproves the findings of Khoiri et al. (2021) that environmental awareness is mostly overlooked by students as part of their character education because the respondents in this study acquired a high level of environmental awareness which highlights the importance of the environment in their actions.

Regarding the Conscious Consumption indicator, respondents obtained a high level which means that Generation Z students are strongly conscious of their manner of consumption that could affect the environment. In a survey conducted among Gen Z consumers, it revealed the attitudes and viewpoints underlying Gen Z's shopping habits, demonstrating that members of this generation are conscious consumers concerned about sustainability and keen to express their individuality (Driver, 2021). Same author suggested that they are considerably persuaded to buy products based on a brand's attempts to lessen its environmental footprint and use of eco-friendly materials. This demonstrated that Gen Zs are intentionally concerned with brands' sustainability credentials, both in terms of social and environmental concerns.

Furthermore, data revealed that the Waste and Recycling indicator of Generation Z is very high which means that respondents are highly aware of the importance of proper waste management and recycling to the environment. To support this, a study from the University of Bath found that the generation aged 16 to 25 is rejecting the harmful implications of certain lifestyles and seeking solutions to the current environmental crisis. Having grown up with and around technology, Generation Zs may be more aware of its applications. One of its benefits, for example, is that it reduces paper waste. Significantly reduces one's carbon footprint impact. By embracing a 'zero-waste' lifestyle, they are encouraging brands to ditch single-use goods. Instead, they are now developing more durable things by creating things using recyclable or sustainable materials like wood or bamboo. In this regard, younger generations are increasingly emphasizing the significance of sustainable waste management (Ruiz, 2021).

Meanwhile, in understanding the Energy Saving behavior, the data revealed a high level which indicates that Generation Z students are strongly aware about the importance of saving energy resources to the environment. To support this, a study by Dai and Chen (2021) in a Midwestern university in America showed that Generation Z's behavioral intention to switch from traditional light bulbs to energy-efficient ones was predicted by their attitudes, perceived norms, and control beliefs. Same authors claimed that Generation Z's preference towards energy-efficient lighting might not be surprising as their members are often the driving force in environmental activism and behaviors.

Moreover, the data on the awareness of Sustainable Environment showed a high level which means that Generation Z students strongly agree on actions that helps the environment become sustainable in the long run. According to a study by Dobrowolski et al. (2022) in Poland, Generation Z's awareness of the crucial role of companies in upholding sustainable development principles enhances their behavior as consumers in ways of avoiding the waste of food and energy, reducing the shopping of unnecessary goods, and imposing sanctions to companies who are harming the environment. It also corresponds to the findings of Yamane and Kaneko (2021) that when Gen Zs learn about the intrinsic nature of sustainable development goals, they may modify their behavior.

Overall, the exhibited levels of awareness in conscious consumption, waste and recycling, energy saving, and sustainable environment that encompass the variable of environmental awareness reflects how Generation Z highly considers the importance of their actions towards the environment they live in— may it be in ways of responsible waste disposal, turning-off of appliances, and highlighting

individual obligations that are environmentally friendly and sustainable.

Level of Sustainability Perception and Attitude of Generation Z Students

The level of sustainability perception and attitude of Generation Z students is demonstrated in Table 5. The table includes the mean, the standard deviation, and the descriptive level of the data gathered from 382 respondents.

Table 5. *Level of Sustainability Perception and Attitude of Generation Z Students*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Perception	4.24	0.503	Very High
Attitude	4.29	0.545	Very High
Sustainability Perception and Attitude	4.27	0.490	Very High

For the level of sustainability perception and attitude, the data are generated from the mean of its two indicators: (1) Perception, and (2) Attitude.

For the first indicator, Perception, the mean score is 4.24 which indicates a very high level. For the second indicator, Attitude, the mean score is 4.29 which indicates also a very high level. Overall, the 382 respondents obtained a mean score of 4.27, which indicates that their level of sustainability perception and attitude is very high. Furthermore, the two indicators, Perception, and Attitude have obtained standard deviations of 0.503, and 0.545 respectively. This means that the data points of these indicators are clustered around the mean. Overall, the level of sustainability perception and attitude has obtained a standard deviation of 0.490 which means that there is less variability of the responses.

Since the Perception, and Attitude indicators are on very high levels, the overall level of sustainability perception and attitude is very high as well. This suggested that Generation Z students has a high positive perception and attitude towards sustainability. Consequently, this supported Ramsey and Rickson's (1976) Behavioral Change Model, which claims that with increased knowledge, favorable attitudes that lead to responsible actions emerge. With their high positive perception and attitude towards sustainability showed that this would likely motivate them to behave in a manner that promotes the importance of sustainability.

In a recent report from the University of Pennsylvania, it was determined that when it comes to sustainability-related decisions, Generation Z have considerable influence over previous generations. Also, it revealed that three-quarters of Generation Z perceived that sustainability is more important to them than brand recognition when making purchasing decisions. Frequently, these decisions prioritize limiting consumption, reducing one's carbon footprint, supporting small batch manufacturers and local businesses, engaging in the circular economy, and purchasing previously owned things rather than brand-new ones. Likewise, it was highlighted that Generation Z has consistently remained true to their environmental principles while simultaneously educating and influencing preceding generations (Petro, 2022).

In terms of sustainability perception indicator, the data revealed a very high level which indicates that Generation Z students have a high positive perception towards sustainable behavior. According to a study conducted at a public university in Malaysia, the students' sustainable behavior and conduct reflect their exposure to sustainable development through their educational system. In addition, the data showed that they prioritized education, sustainable energy, cleanliness, and sanitation. Hence, emphasizing the significance of exposure to issues concerning sustainable development in higher education could improve the perception and comprehension among Generation Z students. (Ismail et al., 2022).

In addition, the data on the sustainability attitude showed a very high level which indicates that Generation Z students have a high positive attitude towards promoting sustainable behavior. It corresponds to a study by Dabija (2020) about sustainable orientation of Generation Z in terms of retail in Romania assessed their attitude towards sustainability and have revealed that Generation Zs showed a sense of belonging and responsibility towards their environment and community. It highlighted the importance of being responsible in terms of resource consumption and its consequences. Moreover, Generation Z is seen as having a proactive attitude, as they are willing to become involved not only in combating the harmful impacts of environmental crisis, but also in preventing their occurrence wherever possible. In terms of consumer attitudes toward the environment, respondents from Generation Z stressed that environmental protection and conservation are our collective responsibility.

Consequently, the exhibited levels of sustainability perception and attitude reflects how the Generation Z perceived the importance of promoting sustainable behavior may it be in social, economic, or environmental aspects which are deemed integral components of sustainability.

Significance of the Relationship between Generation Z Students' Environmental Awareness and Sustainability Perception and Attitude

The relationship of environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude of Generation Z students is demonstrated in Table 6. The table includes the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r), the p -value, and the qualitative description of the data gathered from 382 respondents.

Table 6. *Correlation Matrix between Environmental Awareness and Sustainability Perception and Attitude of Generation Z Students*

<i>N</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
382	0.568	0.000	Significant

p-value < $\alpha = 0.05$

The result of the Pearson *r* correlation showed that there was a significant moderate correlation between Environmental Awareness and Sustainability Perception and Attitude, ($r = 0.568$, $p < 0.05$). The results revealed that the *p*-value is lower than the alpha level, hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Moreover, the relationship between the two variables showed a moderate positive relationship which means that as the level of Environmental Awareness increases, the level of Sustainability Perception and Attitude also increases. Yet, when one variable decreases, the other variable decreases too. This portrayed that the more Gen Zs highly consider the importance of environmental awareness in their actions, the higher they hold a positive perception and attitude towards sustainability, and vice-versa.

Correspondingly, in a study by Nikolić et al. (2022) that examined Generation Z's attitudes, behavior, and awareness regarding sustainability-oriented products in two European countries, evidence revealed that there is a statistically significant and relatively strong relation between sustainability and circular economy attitudes and sustainability and circular economy behavior. This demonstrated that Gen Z is more knowledgeable about recycling enterprises than it is about the circular economy, even though the great majority of them are worried about the future of the planet and are encouraged to learn more through awareness-raising initiatives. Similarly, in a study that explored the interaction between environmental consciousness and sustainable food attributes in the United States, Gen Z consumers with high environmental consciousness and moderate ecological awareness gave more consideration to eco-friendly and healthy product attributes when buying sustainable food, whereas Gen Z consumers with low environmental consciousness gave more weight to extrinsic product attributes like price and convenience (Su et al., 2019).

In discussions of environmental issues, a study by Kousar et al. (2022) revealed that the climate change awareness significantly and positively affects climate-friendly behavior, environmental quality, and pro-environmental behavior of students in public and private higher educational institutions in Pakistan. It implied that to protect the environment, it is crucial to raise students' understanding of climate and climate change-related concerns. Thus, it agrees to the findings of Barron et al. (2022) that climate change discussions may become part of Gen Zs transformative curriculum. Comparably, Punzalan (2020) investigated the correlation between the level of environmental awareness and extent of practices among the senior high school students in the Philippines. It was revealed that the level of awareness of students is significantly related to their degree of practice along the four environmental themes namely: stewardship, finiteness of resources, change, and materials cycle. However, same author noted that students have a good level of environmental awareness but poor level of environmental practice which yielded a contrasting result in this study since the Generation Z students acquired a high level of environmental awareness and very high level of sustainability perception and attitude.

Furthermore, a study by Mkumbachi (2020) amongst 18–23-year-old students university students in Indonesia revealed that most students possessed higher environmental awareness and showed high pro-environment behavior. There was a strong correlation between environmental awareness and pro-environmental behavior, indicating that students have a higher level of environmental awareness and knowledge of environmental issues. This can be attributed to their access to a wider variety of media, which encourages their ability to acquire content and information on environmental issues. This is similar to the findings of this study as Generation Z students have garnered a high level of environmental awareness and very high sustainability perception and attitude. This means that students learn from a variety of sources regarding environmental concern which heightened their awareness towards these issues while also engaging in sustainable behavior. This finding contradicts the observation of Nahar et al. (2022) that people in Bangladesh are aware of the need to adopt a pro-environment mindset, but they do not engage in any environmental practice. Correspondingly, in another study by Wang et al. (2023) on Chinese university students' environmentally sustainable behavior toward tourism destinations, the results exhibited a positive direct relationship between environmental awareness and biosphere, altruistic and egoistic values. The researchers also discovered that the previously stated characteristics are highly indicative of environmentally sustainable behavior, which implies the need for a campaign to encourage such behavior among college students while also taking environmental awareness into consideration. In addition, it was shown that among Malaysian university students, a moral commitment to sustainability is positively correlated with increased sustainability awareness, a motivation to protect sustainability, and a sense of responsibility towards sustainable development. In other words, respondents were thought to have a basic understanding of sustainable development (Tang et al., 2018).

On a more practical implication, not only are Gen Zs aware of the environmental difficulties the globe is facing, but they also think that the concerns of poverty, inequality, unemployment, and the economy are equally significant and will become more relevant over the course of their lifetimes (Sustainability Knowledge Group, 2020). The Generation Z's knowledge of environmental, social, and economic challenges serves as an urgent warning to businesses to change their models and include sustainability concepts into both their daily operations and company strategy. Since they are more prepared than Millennials to act and take ownership of mistakes done by earlier generations, it follows that they may even go so far as to boycott unsustainable businesses. In a similar analysis of Hidayat and Hidayat (2021), Generation Z exhibits a comparatively high level of concern about the planet's future as they connect it to their own and the future of humanity. Same authors suggest that the majority of Generation Z are deeply concerned about the harmful effects of development that takes advantage of nature, imbalanced ecosystems, and the lack of awareness among humans about environmental

sustainability.

With the findings of relevant studies above, it can be inferred that Generation Zs inclination towards sustainability is acquired through the awareness of environmental issues by media exposure, personal preferences, and education. Thus, by evidence and practical implications, their environmental awareness has a significant link on how they perceive sustainability and act upon it.

Conclusions

Considering the results and discussions presented, the following conclusions are drawn:

With the current environmental crisis that the world is facing right now compels every individual to take action in the preservation of nature and to redirect their efforts on approaches that are environmentally friendly. Considerably, as Generation Zs have matured into young adults, their collective voice has become a greater force within the world at large.

It was revealed that the Generation Z students have high level of environmental awareness with a mean level of 3.98 which indicates that they highly consider the importance of environmental awareness in their actions. Given that their high level of awareness has emphasized a practical-based approach wherein it showed the importance of being consciously aware of resources consumption, a high regard of maintaining proper waste management, being strongly aware about the importance of saving energy resources to the environment and aligning their actions to ways that helps the environment become sustainable in the long run.

Furthermore, it was also revealed that the Generation Z students have a very high level of sustainability perception and attitude with a mean level of 4.27 which indicates that they have a high positive perception and attitude towards sustainable behavior. In line with this, it emphasizes that their decisions are sensitive towards promoting sustainability. Also, Generation Z students highlighted the importance of cultivating a proactive attitude it terms of social, economic, and environmental aspects which are the significant key components of sustainability.

Lastly, it showed that there is a moderate positive relationship between environmental awareness and sustainability perception and attitude of the Generation Z students with the *r*-value of 0.568. Given that, as their level of environmental awareness increases, their sustainability perception and attitude increase as well. This revealed that with the Generation Z students' heightened knowledge and awareness in terms of the environment, there is also a heightened positive perception and attitude towards promoting sustainability with regards to the society, economy, and environment.

Based on the preceding findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are drawn:

To enhance the knowledge of students on environmental issues and orient their actions towards sustainability, the authors recommended for a stronger integration of environmental information in college curriculum. It was to ensure that despite having a high level of environmental awareness and very high level of sustainability perception and attitude, students continue to take account of environmental concerns and prioritize sustainability in their lifestyles.

Moreover, the researchers also suggested the university to strengthen its pro-environment policies which can be done through imposition of stricter sanctions on violations and comprehensive instruction regarding these guidelines to empower more students to become conscious in their actions towards the environment.

Also, teachers and faculty members are recommended to reinforce pro- environment behaviors in students by educating them of their crucial role in saving the environment for future generations. On the other hand, students are encouraged to take learning about environmental affairs more seriously and explore other sustainable practices in their generation like purchasing pre-owned clothing, patronizing local companies, and being wise in their purchasing decisions for a greener practice.

Lastly, the authors suggested future researchers to further investigate the factors and mediating influences that could affect how students perceive the environment and the concept of sustainable development. This can be done through employing other variables that relate to environment and sustainability or using another research design that opens a newer perspective of investigation. Also, future researchers may utilize the samples from other cohorts or generations and increase the number of respondents for a more comparative view and wider scope of study.

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